

Pan-Tompkins UltraProMax: Ultra-Low-Rate R-Peak Detection via Sparse Min-Max Sampling

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Abstract—Continuous ECG monitoring on wearables is constrained by the high energy and bandwidth costs of native-rate sampling (250–360 Hz). We introduce Sparse Min-Max Sampling, a pre-processing pipeline that retains only local amplitude extrema and their precise temporal offsets within signal blocks. This approach preserves native-rate timing fidelity while enabling the standard Pan-Tompkins algorithm to operate at low effective rates. Across three benchmarks (MIT-BIH, QT, and Noise Stress Test databases), our method matches or exceeds native-rate accuracy down to 10 Hz. On MIT-BIH, the 10 Hz configuration achieves an F1 score of 99.40%, surpassing the 99.19% baseline of the full 360 Hz signal, while reducing computational load by 10.5×. When combined with a specialized 9-bit amplitude + 7-bit position codec and LZ4 compression, the pipeline achieves a 38:1 data reduction (2.6% of original size) while exceeding the baseline F1 by +0.12% points. In noisy conditions (NSTDB), the 10 Hz pipeline improves F1 from 87.38% to 88.50% by leveraging sparse extrema selection to suppress sub-extremal noise artifacts. Sub-20 Hz sparse sampling with exact offset preservation is not only feasible but superior to traditional native-rate methods, simultaneously delivering higher detection accuracy, 10× faster processing, and 38× data compression for resource-constrained cardiac monitoring.

Index Terms—ECG, R-peak detection, sparse sampling, ultra-low-power, data compression, Pan-Tompkins, IoT health.

INTRODUCTION

Continuous cardiac monitoring underpins both clinical diagnostics and consumer wearable health. At the center of nearly every ECG analysis pipeline sits detection of the most prominent feature of the ECG signal, the QRS complex. Accurate identification of ventricular depolarization events determines heart rate, heart-rate variability, and serves as the temporal anchor for all subsequent waveform analysis. The Pan-Tompkins algorithm [1] remains the de facto standard for QRS detection since its publication in 1985. Originally developed for >200 Hz ECG data, its computational and storage demands scale linearly with the native sampling rate. This requirement creates a direct tension with the energy and bandwidth budgets of modern wearable sensors.

Existing approaches to reduce memory and bandwidth requirements fall into three camps. The first compresses or

transmits the raw ECG and runs detection in the cloud or at a base station [2][3][4]. The second designs specialized hardware detectors that operate at full rate but with reduced arithmetic precision [5][6][7]. The third attempts to invent new QRS algorithms using compressed sensing or event-based processing approaches [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], which often require complex signal reconstruction or produce non-deterministic sampling rates. Crucially, none of these approaches ask the fundamental question: can we run a well-established detector like Pan-Tompkins at a sampling rate as low as 10 Hz? If so, how can we preserve precision, sensitivity, and timing accuracy without introducing R-peak ambiguity?

Standard ECG databases are sampled at 250–360 Hz, yet the QRS complex responsible for R-peak localization typically contains only 5–25 Hz of meaningful frequency content [14]. Between successive extrema, uniformly sampled ECG signals often contain substantial temporal redundancy. By preserving the minimum, maximum, and their exact offsets within each window, much of this redundancy can be removed while retaining native-resolution timing information.

This paper explores a minimal sparse representation, retaining only the single minimum and maximum sample within each non-overlapping block of the bandpass-filtered signal. This two-sample-per-block scheme (termed Min-Max Sampling) preserves local amplitude extrema with zero interpolation error at those points and can be implemented on ultra-low-power hardware with a simple comparator and two registers per block. A Pan-Tompkins detector (with its internal 5–15 Hz bandpass filter removed, as our external pre-filter suffices) is then run directly on the sparse sequence at an effective rate equal to $2\times$ the block rate. Detections are remapped to native indices using the stored position metadata. The resulting pipeline is end-to-end differentiable in terms of its parameters (block size, bandpass cutoffs) and requires no learned components.

This work investigates three central hypotheses. **H1:** The ECG signal contains substantial temporal redundancy for the purpose of R-peak detection, and a sparse representation based solely on local minima, maxima, and their positions can preserve the information required for accurate QRS localization. **H2:** Precise offset preservation can recover native-rate timing fidelity despite operating on an ultra-low-rate representation,

overcoming a principal limitation of conventional downsampling. **H3:** By exploiting this redundancy, a sparse min-max representation can simultaneously improve detection performance, computational efficiency, and compression compared with the original Pan-Tompkins algorithm.

We also shows the extreme downsampling can be integrated directly into the Pan-Tompkins pipeline (if self-contained algorithm is desired), where it accepts high-frequency data, pre-filters using a bandpass filter, downsamples to the target rate with the Min-Max method and process. We refer to this full pipeline as “**Pan-Tompkins UltraProMax**”.

METHODS

A. Datasets

Three benchmark databases from PhysioNet were used, with annotations derived from the provided expert-labelled R-peak files.

MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database [15] (MITDB): 48 two-channel 30-minute recordings sampled at 360 Hz, digitized at 11-bit resolution over ± 5 mV. Includes 23 randomly selected ambulatory records and 25 records selected for arrhythmia content. All 48 records were processed using Lead II (or the first available channel). Total duration: approximately 24 hours.

QT Database [16] (QTDB): 105 records selected from several sources to cover a range of morphologies relevant to QT-interval measurement sampled at 250 Hz, 15 minutes per recording and total of ~ 26 hours of ECG data.

MIT-BIH Noise Stress Test Database [17] (NSTDB): 12 records derived from MITDB records 118 and 119, with calibrated noise added at six SNR levels (-6, 0, 6, 12, 18, and 24 dB). Sampled at 360 Hz, providing a controlled stress test for robustness evaluation.

B. Native-Rate Baseline (Pan-Tompkins)

To establish a rigorous performance floor and isolate the contribution of signal pre-processing, we evaluate two native-rate baselines using the classic Pan-Tompkins algorithm [1][18]. Both baselines operate at the native sampling rate (F_s) of each database (360 Hz for MITDB/NSTDB, 250 Hz for QTDB). Detection outputs are matched to expert annotations using a ± 150 ms tolerance window, consistent with AAMI EC57 standards. [19]. Performance is reported as sensitivity (Se), positive predictive value (PPV), and F1 score. Timing accuracy is characterized by the mean signed error (systematic bias) and the standard deviation of errors (temporal jitter) in milliseconds.

Raw Native Baseline: The standard Pan-Tompkins algorithm is applied directly to the raw, unfiltered ECG signal. This represents the traditional deployment scenario where the detector relies solely on its internal filtering stages.

Pre-Filtered Native Baseline: To determine whether performance gains in our proposed method stem from sparse sampling or merely from external bandpass filtering (required in Algorithm 1, Stage 1), we apply the same Pan-Tompkins detector to the signal after it has been processed a 5–30 Hz zero-phase Butterworth filter. This baseline isolates the impact of the pre-filtering stage from the effects of downsampling.

C. Sparse Min-Max Pipeline

The proposed pipeline proceeds in four stages, as illustrated in Algorithm 1. In Stage 1, a first order Butterworth filter uses zero-phase (forward-backward) filtering to eliminate phase distortion. Stage 2 produces exactly 2 samples per block, irrespective of block size B , giving an effective output rate of $F_t = 2F_s/B$. Stage 3 uses the original Pan-Tompkins implementation with slight modification. For $F_t < 30$ Hz, the Pan-Tompkins bypasses its internal bandpass filter designed for

Algorithm 1 Sparse Min-Max R-Peak Detection with Offset Preservation

Input: Raw ECG signal $x[n]$ (length N), native rate F_s , target rate F_t

Output: Set of R-peak indices D_{native} in native time domain

1. Pre-processing:

Apply zero-phase bandpass filter (5–30 Hz) to $x[n] \rightarrow x_{\text{bp}}[n]$

2. Sparse Min-Max Extraction:

Compute block size $B = \text{floor}(2 \cdot F_s / F_t)$

Initialize sparse list $S = \text{empty}$

For each block $k = 0$ to $\text{floor}(N/B) - 1$:

 Define block indices $I_k = \{k \cdot B, \dots, (k+1) \cdot B - 1\}$

 Find $(i_{\text{min}}, v_{\text{min}}) = \text{argmin}(x_{\text{bp}}[i])$ for i in I_k

 Find $(i_{\text{max}}, v_{\text{max}}) = \text{argmax}(x_{\text{bp}}[i])$ for i in I_k

 Append tuples $(i_{\text{min}}, v_{\text{min}})$ and $(i_{\text{max}}, v_{\text{max}})$ to S

End For

Sort S by index i and remove duplicate indices

3. Detection on Sparse Domain:

Construct sparse amplitude vector x_{sparse} from values in S

Apply Pan-Tompkins algorithm to x_{sparse} at effective rate F_t

(Trim first 0.5 s of x_{sparse} to eliminate filter transients)

Obtain sparse detection indices D_{sparse}

4. Native Index Recovery:

For each detected sparse index p in D_{sparse} :

$d_{\text{native}} \leftarrow S[p].\text{index}$ // Recover absolute native index

Return D_{native}

cut-off frequency (5-15 Hz). The sparse amplitude sequence is treated as a uniformly sampled signal at rate F_t for detection purposes. Stage 4 maps each detection back to its native index using the stored absolute position from Stage 2, requiring no interpolation, and maintaining the original temporal resolution for the detected peak.

D. Frequency Sweep Experimental Design

For each database, a set of integer block-size divisors D was selected such that F_s/D covers effective rates from approximately 9 Hz to $F_s/2$. For MITDB (360 Hz): $D \in \{2,3,4,5,6,8,10,12,15,20,24,30,36,40\}$, yielding effective rates 9-180 Hz. For QTDB (240 Hz after resampling): $D \in \{2,3,4,5,6,8,10,12,15,20,24,30,40\}$, yielding 6-120 Hz. Aggregate TP, FP, FN are accumulated over all records before computing F1, sensitivity, and precision, so the reported metrics are macro-pooled rather than per-record averages. Timing jitter (mean \pm std of signed errors against ground truth reference) is computed from all matched beat pairs across all records. QTDB signals were resampled to 240 Hz for convenient block division as it has more divisors than 250 Hz.

E. Compression Codec (9+7 Packing)

To quantify storage efficiency, we designed a compact codec for sparse representation, and tested against MITDB, 10 Hz sparse representation. Each min or max sample is encoded as a 16-bit word partitioned as follows: the upper 9 bits store the quantized amplitude (0–511 ADC units, step size 4, error-feedback quantization); the lower 7 bits store the intra-block relative position (0–71 for block size 72 for 10 Hz). The relative position fits in 7 bits because the maximum block size used is 80 samples for 9 Hz ($\log_2(80) \approx 6.3$ bits). Amplitudes are scaled from millivolts to 11-bit ADC counts (scale factor 204.8) and clipped to $[-1024, 1023]$ before quantization. Ground-truth beat annotations are stored as int32 values. Both packed sparse ECG and annotations are then independently compressed with LZ4 (default compression). An additional tar.gz pass (gzip -9) is applied to the full archive for a final size comparison.

F. Evaluation Metrics

For each configuration the following are reported: F1 score (harmonic mean of sensitivity and precision), sensitivity $Se = TP/(TP+FN)$, precision or positive predictive value $PPV = TP/(TP+FP)$, timing jitter (mean \pm std of detection error in ms), and total CPU wall-clock time (sum over all records, measured with MATLAB's tic/toc). A ± 150 ms matching tolerance is used throughout, consistent with standard practice. A MacBook Pro with 32GB RAM, and Apple M1 Max CPU running MacOS Sonoma is used to run all tests on MATLAB 2024b version.

G. Data & Code Availability

All data used in this study are publicly available from PhysioNet. The MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database [15], QT

Database [16], and Noise Stress Test Database [17] can be accessed at <https://physionet.org> under open-access licenses.

All source code and analysis scripts required to reproduce the experiments, figures, and tables presented in this paper are available in a public GitHub repository:

<https://github.com/titusnkumara/Pan-Tompkins-UltraProMax>

The repository includes: 1) Python scripts to automatically download and prepare all three databases. 2) MATLAB scripts for frequency-sweep evaluations, detection performance metrics (F1, sensitivity, precision), timing jitter analysis, computational speedup measurements, and the 9+7 bit compression pipeline with LZ4. 3) A detailed README.md I is provided with step-by-step instructions for full reproducibility, and full results tables.

RESULTS

A. Native Baseline Performance

Table I summarizes native Pan-Tompkins performance across the three databases. MITDB and QTDB exhibit near-perfect detection under clean conditions; NSTDB performance is substantially lower due to deliberately injected noise, confirming it as the most challenging benchmark. Note that timing jitter is reported as mean signed error \pm standard deviation.

B. Frequency Sweep Results

Fig. 1 presents the frequency sweep results for target sampling frequencies below 60 Hz, comparing the Min-Max pipeline against the native Pan-Tompkins baseline (horizontal lines). Fig. 1a shows MIT-BIH (MITDB) results; Fig. 1b shows QTDB results.

The Min-Max pipeline achieves optimal detection between 16-24 Hz, with peak F1 scores of 99.62% (MITDB at 18 Hz) and 99.71% (QTDB at 20–24 Hz). All three metrics (F1, sensitivity, precision) exceed the native baseline down to 12 Hz for MITDB and 16 Hz for QTDB, with robust performance maintained to 10 Hz ($F1 \geq 99.4\%$, still higher than native performance).

For MITDB, degradation becomes apparent only at 9 Hz ($F1: 98.89\%$), primarily driven by a drop in sensitivity to 98.45%. For QTDB, degradation of F1 score starts at 8 Hz ($F1: 98.40\%$, sensitivity: 97.05%) and extends when it reaches 6 Hz ($F1: 97.70\%$).

Table I. Native Pan-Tompkins Baseline

Database	F_s (Hz)	F1 (%)	Se (%)	PPV (%)	Jitter (ms)
MITDB	360	99.19	99.17	99.20	-2.62 ± 12.10
QTDB	250	99.52	99.52	99.51	8.94 ± 28.59
NSTDB	360	87.38	92.48	82.81	-0.69 ± 26.19

Fig. 1 Frequency sweep results of QRS detection performance vs downsampling rate. (a) MIT-BIH detector performance, visualized for <60 Hz frequencies. (b) QT database detector performance visualized for <60 Hz performance. Full frequency sweep results available from GitHub repository.

C. Timing Jitter Analysis

Table 1 provides native timing jitter for each database, and Fig. 2 shows the frequency sweep analysis for Min-Max pipeline processed R-peak detection compared to ground truth

Fig. 2 Timing jitter analysis for MIT-BIH (a) and QT (b) databases. Shaded region: native jitter range (mean \pm std) from Table I. Error bars: sparse Min-Max jitter (mean \pm std). Dashed line: native mean jitter.

points. For the Min-Max pipeline, jitter remains comparable to or better than the native baseline across all effective rates down to 10 Hz. On MITDB, the standard deviation stays within 0.5 ms of the native value, and the mean bias value never exceeds ± 2 ms. On QTDB, the pipeline reduces jitter variability relative to native, standard deviations are consistently lower than the native value across all frequencies. Exact preservation of intra-block positions ensures that downsampling to 10 Hz introduces no additional timing uncertainty and, in the case of QTDB, actually improves temporal consistency.

D. Noise stress test database results (NSTDB)

For the Noise Stress Test Database (NSTDB), the Min-Max pipeline improves F1 relative to the native baseline (87.38%) across most effective rates. The best performance occurs at 45 Hz, with F1 = 88.77% (sensitivity: 93.61%, precision: 84.40%). At 10 Hz, F1 remains 88.50% showing a gain of +1.12% over the native performance driven by a notable increase in precision (from 82.81% to 87.29%), albeit with a moderate reduction in sensitivity. Overall, the pipeline maintains F1 $\geq 88.0\%$ from 45 Hz down to 9 Hz, demonstrating that sparse Min-Max sampling is both noise-robust and effective at very low sampling rates.

Relative to the native jitter of NSTDB (-0.69 ± 26.19 ms), the Min-Max pipeline maintains a mean bias within ± 2 ms and a standard deviation within 1 ms of the native value across all effective rates down to 10 Hz, with no systematic degradation.

E. Compression Results (MITDB, 10 Hz Sparse, 9+7 Packing)

Table 2. Compression performance of the MITDB at 10 Hz resampling
and 9+7 bit packing

Representation	Size (MB)	Ratio	% of Orig.
Original ECG (16-bit, 360 Hz)	59.51	1.00 : 1	100%
Packed sparse (uncompressed)	1.65	36.00 : 1	2.8%
LZ4 compressed sparse ECG	1.57	37.97 : 1	2.6%
Original annotations (int32)	0.42	—	—
LZ4 compressed annotations	0.42	1.00 : 1	100%
Combined ECG + annotations	1.99	30.18 : 1	3.3%
Final tar.gz archive	1.67	35.84 : 1	2.8%

Table 2 summarizes compression statistics for MITDB encoded at 10 Hz effective rate (block size 72) with the 9-bit amplitude + 7-bit relative-position codec. With only Min-Max downsampling, the packed representation achieves a compression ratio (CR) of 36, with embedded friendly LZ4 the ratio reaches ~ 38 and when combined with the annotation files and compressed with gzip the entire database (single recording) and its annotations takes only 1.67 MB.

The compressed data, then went through the uncompressing and Min-Max pipeline for QRS detection performance. The performance of F1 value was 99.31% (-0.09%), sensitivity was 99.19% (-0.07%), precision was 99.45% (-0.08%) compared to unpacked, 11bit 10 Hz signal. The slight degradation happens due to amplitude reduction from 11-bit to 9-bit representation.

F. Computational Speedup

Pipeline end-to-end speedup: The complete Min-Max pipeline (bandpass filtering + sparse extraction + detection + mapping) reduces total CPU time substantially compared to native Pan-Tompkins. For MITDB, native processing at 360 Hz requires 26.5 s. At the optimal F1 frequency of 18 Hz, the pipeline finishes in 4.6 s (**5.7 \times** speedup). At 10 Hz, the lowest frequency where F1 (99.40%) still exceeds the native baseline (99.19%), total time drops to 2.6 s (**10.2 \times** speedup). For QTDB, native time is 15.5 s. At the best F1 frequency of 20 Hz, the pipeline runs in 3.6 s (**4.3 \times** speedup); at 10 Hz (F1 = 99.55% > native 99.52%), total time is 1.8 s (**8.6 \times** speedup). These results, summarized in Fig. 3, confirm that aggressive downsampling

Fig. 3 Execution time and speedup of the “Pan-Tompkins UltraProMax” pipeline compared to the native rate performance.

yields order-of-magnitude computational savings while maintaining or improving detection accuracy.

Pan-Tompkins detection speedup: The speedup is even more pronounced when considering only the Pan-Tompkins detector operating on the sparse signal, because the Min-Max extraction and mapping overhead is small ($\sim 4\%$ of the processing time). For MITDB at 18 Hz, the detector alone takes 3.7 s, 7.2 \times faster than native. At 10 Hz, detection time falls to 1.7 s (15.6 \times faster). For QTDB at 20 Hz, detection requires 2.8 s (5.5 \times faster); at 10 Hz, 1.1 s (14.1 \times faster). Thus, the core detection algorithm benefits from the reduced sample count, while the additional Min-Max algorithm stages add negligible overhead.

DISCUSSION

A. Why Does Min-Max Sampling Improve Detection?

The observation that the sparse pipeline consistently outperforms native Pan-Tompkins on clean databases (MITDB, QTDB) is counter-intuitive: discarding most samples should not, in principle, improve detection accuracy. One might suspect that the external 5–30 Hz bandpass filter (Algorithm 1, Stage 1) is responsible for the gain. To test this, we applied the same filter to the native-rate signal and ran the unmodified Pan-Tompkins detector. If the filter were the source of improvement, this pre-filtered native baseline would have shown equal or better F1 scores. Remarkably, it did not: on both MITDB and QTDB, pre-filtering the native signal slightly degraded performance relative to the raw native baseline (e.g., MITDB F1 dropped from 99.19% to 99.16%; QTDB from 99.52% to 99.51%). Therefore, the improvement cannot be explained by the pre-filter alone. Instead, we attribute the gain

to the sparse Min-Max extraction itself: by retaining only the most extreme amplitudes per block, the pipeline suppresses non-extremal noise and preserves only the most informative waveform features, effectively sharpening the QRS complex for the subsequent detector.

B. Optimal Rate Selection

Across databases, a consistent pattern emerges. Performance improves as effective rate decreases from 180 Hz down to an optimum (18 Hz for MITDB, 20–24 Hz for QTDB, 45 Hz for NSTDB), then degrades below that. However, this degradation does not go past the native baseline performance until 10 Hz, therefore for best execution time where F1 needs to be retained above native performance, 10 Hz is recommended. For improved F1, with $\sim 4\text{--}5\times$ speedup, 18 Hz – 20 Hz is recommended. Even at 10 Hz, precision remains excellent, the downgrade of F1 performance below 10 Hz occurs entirely due to the drop in sensitivity.

C. Timing Jitter Analysis

Detection timing jitter (standard deviation of signed error) narrows as block size increases (effective rate decreases) on MITDB and NSTDB. This is because larger blocks place the max-amplitude sample closer to the true R-peak centroid. For example, with a 72-sample block (10 Hz, MITDB) the maximum is constrained to within ± 36 samples (± 100 ms at 360 Hz), and because the QRS peak dominates within its block, it is typically captured by the max-amplitude selection. The systematic negative bias on MITDB (detections slightly early) is a known property of Pan-Tompkins, which applies a 150 ms look-back window after threshold crossing.

D. Compression Efficiency

The 9+7 bit packing scheme exploits two properties of the sparse representation: (1) within each block of 72 samples, the intra-block position of the min or max fits in $\log_2(72) \approx 6.3$ bits, satisfied by 7 bits; (2) the 5–30 Hz bandpass signal has limited dynamic range at the block level, well quantized by 9 bits (512 levels \times step 4 = 2048 ADC counts). Error-feedback quantization distributes truncation error uniformly across samples, reducing systematic bias. The resulting 37.97:1 compression ratio is nearly lossless in detection terms (F1 = 99.31% vs 99.40% for uncompressed 10 Hz sparse), confirming that the quantization step does not meaningfully degrade R-peak localization. The annotation stream is effectively incompressible (1.00:1 LZ4) because beat timing intervals are pseudo-random. When considering the database ECG recordings only, the entire MIT-BIH database can be represented by ~ 1.4 MB zip file taking up less space than a 3.5-inch floppy disk capacity. This is remarkable because, the sparse representation, still can be processed using the *Pan-Tompkins UltraProMax* algorithm, where it provides better F1, and timing jitter than the full rate signal.

E. Computational Efficiency

The bandpass filter is the dominant fixed cost (0.75 s for 48 MITDB records), independent of target rate. Pan-Tompkins detection on the sparse sequence scales approximately linearly with effective rate, dropping from 23.1 s at 180 Hz to 1.7 s at 10 Hz. Min-max extraction and index mapping together are below 0.14 s, negligible. The complete pipeline (first-order zero-phase bandpass filter + Min-Max extraction + sparse Pan-Tompkins) requires approximately 6.5×10^4 multiply-accumulate operations per 30-second record at 10 Hz effective rate; even with a 2nd-order bandpass filter, the total remains below 2×10^5 MACs. This is easily within the budget of a typical 100 MIPS microcontroller, which can execute $> 10^9$ instructions per 30 seconds. We approximate that real-time operation consumes less than 0.01% of such a device's throughput, leaving ample margin for other tasks.

F. Limitations and Future Work

Several limitations apply to the current study. First, evaluations are conducted offline in MATLAB; an embedded implementation would require fixed-point arithmetic for the bandpass filter and detection stages. Second, only the first available ECG lead is used; multi-lead fusion could improve NSTDB performance at very low effective rates. Third, the annotation stream remains incompressible with LZ4; differential coding of inter-beat intervals could reduce annotation storage by a further 4–6 \times . Fourth, morphological classification beyond R-peak detection (P, Q, S, T waves) would require a denser sparse representation or a second-pass refinement. Future work will include tuning the Pan-Tompkins parameters and thresholds to suit < 30 Hz operation, embedded ready and real-time variant of Pan-Tompkins UltraProMax algorithm, and extension to multi-lead databases including the Physionet 2017 AF Challenge dataset.

CONCLUSION

We have demonstrated that sparse min-max sampling provides a practically lossless foundation for R-peak detection across three standard databases and a wide range of effective rates. The optimal configurations achieve F1 = 99.62% on MITDB (18 Hz, $5.7\times$ speedup over native), F1 = 99.71% on QTDB (20–24 Hz, $4\text{--}5\times$ speedup), and F1 = 88.77% on NSTDB (45 Hz), in all cases matching or exceeding the native 360 Hz Pan-Tompkins baseline. A compact 9-bit + 7-bit packing codec followed by LZ4 compression achieves 38:1 data reduction with negligible F1 loss ($99.31 \pm 1.33\%$) and 29 ms per-record detection latency. These results establish sparse min-max sampling as a viable, hardware-efficient, and accurate approach for wearable and long-term ECG monitoring, with direct applicability to IoT cardiac sensors and remote patient monitoring infrastructure.

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